

An Investigation of Gender-Based Sensitivity of College Students

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Abstract

Gender-based sensitivity is relevant to the quality of research that contributes to our understanding of causal pathways. The researchers aimed to investigate whether the differences in age, gender, and school existed in the gender-based sensitivity towards college students in a higher education institution. The researchers utilized descriptive design which described the practices of the institution in gender equality in every transaction. The researchers utilized convenience sampling technique due to its accessibility to the respondents to answer the research questionnaire. The results showed that most of the respondents are aged 21-25 years old, females, and mostly under the School of Health Science Professions program. Among all the parameters, co-curricular and extracurricular activities got the highest mean score of 2.32. The lowest mean score in parameters is pedagogical practices with a score of 1.73. There is a significant difference in terms of pedagogical practices and school administrations when grouped according to age. This research advances our understanding of the issue and provides some partial solutions to address the institution's gender sensitivity concerns. The researchers recommended an integration of gender sensitivity in every transaction in the institution. A more equal provision of school administrators and, ideally, gender transformative preventative programs for both men and women, requires determining the importance and well-founded inclusion or exclusion of gender sensitivity and thorough study.

Keywords: Gender sensitivity. Educational system. Gender. Students. Higher education institution.

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Introduction

Gender refers to the biological and physiological characteristics that define men and women. It also refers to the socially constructed roles, attitudes, habits, and characteristics that a culture finds suitable for men and women in that society. Although sex is permanent and universal, gender is formed differently in different cultures. To put it another way, the words "male" and "female" are sex categories, while "masculine" and "feminine" are classified as gender categories.

Gender sensitivity is the act of becoming aware of how others perceive gender. It aims to make people less reliant on assumptions around stereotypical and distorted views about men and women's roles. People's language choices are often used to express their emotions, so we should use more inclusive vocabulary and gender-neutral terminology.

Gender patriarchal terms are not harmless; by making women less visible, society will view them as having less merit. Both men and women prosper from gender equity because it expands their options. In a social or interpersonal interaction, a gender identity is a collection of social and behavioral expectations that are usually considered suitable for either a male or a female.

As stipulated in the research introduction of Obiunu (2013), gender or sex refers to the roles, attributes, and values that women and men are given by the culture and community. The attitudes of women and men, as well as their relationship, are described by these roles, attributes, and values. Social organizations such as families, states, neighborhoods, schools, churches, and the media help to establish and sustain all men and women. Certain roles, attributes, and characteristics are assigned to men and women according to their gender.

Gender may also be described as an individual concept based on social attitudes and values that vary by location and change over time, especially in secondary schools and beyond. Moreover, gender sensitivity often refers to a person's understanding of and respect for the importance of ensuring a fair degree of gender distinction between men and women. It is true to some extent that what a man can do, the woman can do as well; but it is not practical for a woman to insist on doing everything a man can do, even if it means jeopardizing nature's given honorific roles of becoming a man or a woman.

Not all college curricula are created equal. In reality, gender inequality pervades most tertiary-level educational curricula as a result of long-held socio-cultural norms that determine women's and men's roles in educational systems (Leathwood & Read, 2008).

The researchers aimed to determine the institutional gender-based sensitivity paradigm in the educational system of St. Dominic College of Asia. It answers the following questions: (1) What are the profile variables of the respondents: Age, Gender, and School? (2) What are the institutional gender-based sensitivity parameters of St. Dominic College of Asia in terms of: Co-curricular & Extra Curricular, Gender-based management, School Support Mechanism, Curricular Approach, Course Materials, Pedagogical Practices, School Management, School Infrastructure and utilities and School Administration? (3) Is there a significant difference in the institutional gender based sensitivity when grouped according to demographic profile?

Methodology

The researchers utilized a descriptive design. According to Polit & Beck (2012), this design aims to observe, explain, and record aspects of a situation as they occur naturally, and to sometimes serve as a springboard for generating hypothesis. In this study, the researchers employed this design to describe the practices of the institution in gender equality in every transaction.

Research Population

Four-hundred forty-three (443) students participated in this study: 32 participants came from the School of Arts, Sciences, and Education, 17 from School of Business and Computer Studies, 11 from School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management, and 383 from School of Health Science Professions. All of them were enrolled for First Semester, Academic Year 2019-2020 in St. Dominic College of Asia.

Sampling Technique

The proponents of this study utilized convenience sampling. Saunders, et al. (2012) said that convenience sampling is a method of sampling in which the researcher uses the first available primary data source without any additional criteria. To put it another way, this sampling process entailed gathering participants anywhere they could be found, which was usually wherever it was possible. No inclusion criteria were identified prior to the selection of subjects. All subjects are invited to participate depending on their availability. In this research, the researchers utilized this technique for the accessibility of the respondents to answer the research questionnaire.

Research Instrument

The research questionnaire is composed of the profile variables of the respondents such as age, gender, and school. This is followed by answering the gender sensitivity parameters questionnaire. The tool was scored using the four-point Likert scale: (3) Strongly Agree, (2) Agree, (1) Disagree, and (0) Strongly Disagree. The instruments underwent validation by two respective experts in education and nursing services and a sociologist. Pilot testing was conducted to the 40 students and tested for its reliability with score of 0.86 which means the tool is highly reliable.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents the profile variables of the respondents. With a total of 443 SDCA students as respondents, in terms of age, most of the respondents were aged from 21 to 25 years old with 79.0%, which they are called as “millennials” and are well-oriented with gender equality. Respondents from 26 to 30 years old were 17.2% which they are more goal-oriented regardless of their gender, while the remaining is 3.8%.

In terms of gender, most of the respondents are females with 58.2%, while the male respondents with 41.8%. It is found that females are more exposed to gender sensitivity compared to male respondents. Most of the students from SHSP were 86.5% who answered the questionnaire, followed by SASE (7.2%), SBCS (3.8%), and SIHTM (2.5%).

Table 1 Demographic profile of the respondents (n=443)

	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age	21-25 years old	350	79.0%
	26-30 years old	76	17.2%
	31 years old-above	17	3.8%
Gender	Male	185	41.8%
	Female	258	58.2%
Program	SASE	32	7.2%
	SBCS	17	3.8%
	SIHTM	11	2.5%
	SHSP	383	86.5%

Table 2 shows the institutional gender-based sensitivity in St. Dominic College of Asia. Results revealed that in co-curricular & extracurricular activities, it got the highest mean score of 2.32; to be followed by gender based management with a score of 2.15, school support mechanism (2.02) and curricular approach (2.00). The least mean score of 1.73 pertains to pedagogical practices. The co-curricular parameter focuses on academic activities while the extracurricular is more on the developmental activities of the students. These areas of parameters show gender sensitivity in dealing with the institutional activities. Other parameters focused on their respective tasks to promote gender sensitivity. With a total mean score of 1.95, majority of the students agreed to practice gender sensitivity in the institution.

Table 2 Institutional gender-based sensitivity in St. Dominic College of Asia

No.	Institutional Gender-Based Sensitivity	Mean	Interpretation
1.	Co-Curricular and Extra-Curricular Activities	2.32	Agree to Practice Gender Sensitivity
2.	Gender Based Management	2.15	Agree to Practice Gender Sensitivity
3.	School Support Mechanism	2.02	Agree to Practice Gender Sensitivity
4.	Curricular Approach	2.00	Agree to Practice Gender Sensitivity
5.	Course Materials	1.80	Agree to Practice Gender Sensitivity
6.	Pedagogical Practices	1.73	Agree to Practice Gender Sensitivity
7.	School Management	1.85	Agree to Practice Gender Sensitivity
8.	School Infrastructure and Utilities	1.84	Agree to Practice Gender Sensitivity
9.	School Administration	1.85	Agree to Practice Gender Sensitivity
Total Mean Score		1.95	Agree to Practice Gender Sensitivity

Legend:

- 2.50-3.00: Strongly Agree to Practice Gender Sensitivity
- 1.50-2.49: Agree to Practice Gender Sensitivity
- 1.00-1.49: Disagree to Practice Gender Sensitivity
- 1.00 below: Strongly Disagree to Practice Gender Sensitivity

Co-curricular participation pertains to the factors that were influential in their decision to participate in such activities (Ashton, 2017; Howard, 1986; Pascarella and Terenzini, 2005; Rosson, et al., 1973). Despite the significant amount of literature related to the importance of student involvement in co-curricular activities and its potential impact on retention and the promotion of other educational gains, little research exists regarding millennial students and their perceptions of co-curricular activities. More specifically, there is a lack of research on nontraditional students' level of desire to participate in co-curricular activities, factors detrimental to their decision to participate, and their perception of the benefits of participating.

In a study by Campaan (2016), off-campus jobs, academic demands, and a lack of interest and comfort in engaging in current co-curricular and extracurricular activities are barriers to nontraditional students' involvement. Therefore, a needs evaluation can be useful in determining how to overcome these barriers. This information, as well as more in-depth assessments, could be utilized to schedule co-curricular activities at times more conducive to nontraditional students' participation. Childcare programs and family-oriented activities should be developed by student affairs professionals to increase the participation of this student population. Finally, administrators should explore ways to increase on-campus employment opportunities, such as increased financial aid or fundraising campaigns aimed directly at nontraditional students (Campaan, 2016).

In Table 3, in determining if there is a significant difference in the institutional gender-based sensitivity according to age and school, Table 3 shows that there is no significant difference in the gender-based parameters. However, with regards to gender specifically in pedagogical practices ($p=0.013$) & school administration ($p=0.021$) results indicated that there is a significant difference in the institutional gender-based sensitivity, whereas the rest have no significant difference at all.

Table 3 Significant difference of institutional gender-based sensitivity to profile variables

Variables	Gender-Based Sensitivity Parameters	Sig.	Interpretation
Age	Co-Curricular & Extra Curricular	0.760	Not Significant
	Gender Based Violence	0.421	Not Significant
	School Support Mechanism	0.815	Not Significant
	Curricular Approach	0.318	Not Significant
	Course Materials	0.583	Not Significant
	Pedagogical Practices	0.250	Not Significant
	School Management	0.638	Not Significant
	School Infrastructure and Utilities	0.362	Not Significant
	School Administration	0.453	Not Significant
Gender	Co-Curricular & Extra Curricular	0.677	Not Significant
	Gender Based Violence	0.336	Not Significant
	School Support Mechanism	0.071	Not Significant
	Curricular Approach	0.089	Not Significant
	Course Materials	0.222	Not Significant
	Pedagogical Practices	0.013	Significant
	School Management	0.272	Not Significant
	School Infrastructure and Utilities	0.098	Not Significant
	School Administration	0.021	Significant
School	Co-Curricular & Extra Curricular	0.471	Not Significant
	Gender Based Violence	0.768	Not Significant
	School Support Mechanism	0.876	Not Significant
	Curricular Approach	0.425	Not Significant
	Course Materials	0.064	Not Significant
	Pedagogical Practices	0.308	Not Significant
	School Management	0.257	Not Significant
	School Infrastructure and Utilities	0.742	Not Significant
	School Administration	0.973	Not Significant

Level of Significance: <0.05

According to Lau & Yuen (2010), when compared to males focusing only the concrete random patterns, females preferred both concrete sequential and abstract. This means that learning gender-related responsive pedagogical strategies should be taught at the university level based on the findings the researchers observed, whereas gender-neutral practices as well as gender-sensitive approach are needed to address the needs of female students.

In a same study by Chisholm (2001), the researcher argued that the developments of leaders in a gender-sensitive country can be explained by the particular constructs and practices of leadership in educational administration that associate leadership and competence with masculinity, rationality, and femininity. It is noted that leadership experience, visibility and recognition, and balance were found between public and private institutions. Overall, this pushed women out of their comfort zones, particularly black women who trusted in maternal feminism's collective strengths and capabilities.

Conclusions

To finally summarize, the institution's gender-based sensitivity was measured through its parameters. The results show that most of the respondents are aged from 21 to 25 years old, females, and mostly under the School of Health Science Professions.

The highest mean score is found in the co-curricular and extra-curricular activities. This means that the school is focused on developing and engaging a gender development program for both sexes. Results also indicated that pedagogical practices in gender based sensitivity were significantly different in terms of gender (0.013) and school administration with score of 0.021 following the level of significance of 0.05.

This shows that the institutional gender based sensitivity is practiced in every transaction made in St. Dominic College of Asia. This research advances our understanding of the issue and suggests some partial remedies to alleviate the concern of gender sensitivity to the institution. Although further studies are required to validate the result, it acts as a research manifesto for members of the SDCA community who are considering adopting creative pedagogical practices to close the gender gap. The researchers expect more female involvement in other areas as a result of numerous remedial measures, and hence the gender issue is resolved. This study provides good practice examples of gender sensitivity in an educational institution. Gender-based sensitivity is relevant to the quality of research that contributes to our understanding of causal pathways. A more equal provision of school administrators and, ideally, gender transformative preventative programs for both men and women, requires determining the importance and well-founded inclusion or exclusion of gender sensitivity and thorough study.

Recommendations

The following recommendations suggest to promote and develop Gender-Responsive Curricular Programs which include gender mainstreaming strategies in St. Dominic College of Asia's institutional development plan which includes: training in gender analysis of sexism and other forms of gender biases in curricular design, learning material, pedagogical strategies and disciplinary policies; information dissemination on gender-responsive student success assessment protocols and tools; and instruction in mainstreaming specific and adequate gender-related issues into existing/ongoing courses across different disciplines.

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